

Simulator work about electrical marine propulsion system in dynamic modes

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Abstract:

This paper investigates a simulator work which is used for training, testing, and performance analysis of electrical marine propulsion. It provides training for operators to manage the propulsion system in different scenarios; it helps the engineer to model the performance of the propulsion system under various operational conditions, helping him to develop new designs before implementation. This simulator allows to users to simulate different operational scenarios of the propulsion system: in open water, intermediate mode and ice mode. This system features a steerable, podded electric drive that allows for more efficient maneuverability and reduced fuel consumption in vessels, particularly in ice-breaking and other challenging maritime conditions.

The simulator work includes two low-power electric drives: asynchronous and synchronous on one shaft, the synchronous drive operates in the motor mode, and the asynchronous drive in the generator mode, providing a given load characteristic for the synchronous drive. Purpose of the work removing the performance characteristics of the electric drive at the specified motor and load characteristics of the drive.

1. Introduction:

The simulator work includes two low-power electric drives: asynchronous and synchronous on one shaft, the synchronous drive operates in the motor mode, and the asynchronous drive in the generator mode, providing a given load characteristic for the synchronous drive

PMSM is a synchronous motor with a permanent magnet, the use of permanent magnets allows achieving high efficiency, precise control, and improving performance in various applications, this is due to the desire to reduce the size and weight of the machine [1].

The excitation power and volume of the magnetic system are significantly reduced compared to the classical electromagnetic excitation systems of synchronous machines.

Synchronous motors with electromagnetic excitation during direct start, permanent magnets of the DPM series cannot be "switched off". Therefore, in the process of acceleration, the flux of permanent magnets induces an EMF in the stator winding, under the action of which current flows through the winding through the source. This current, interacting with the field of a permanent magnet, creates a moment similar in nature to the asynchronous moment developed by the stator winding. However, this moment is not a driving one, but a retarding one. The frequency of the current in the stator winding from the field of permanent magnets is proportional to the speed of the rotor [2-6].

Special alternating current electric machines where the EMF induced in the stator by the rotor field. The torque of the motor is the sum of two torques: electromagnetic M_1 , due to the interaction the fields of the stator and rotor, and the reactive moment of the M_2 , due to the unequal conductivity along the longitudinal and transverse axes.

2. Basic information about PMSM:

2.1 Construction: PMSMs consist of a stator with windings and a rotor embedded with permanent magnets. The rotor can be surface-mounted or interior-mounted, influencing the motor's performance characteristics.

2.2 Synchronous Operation: The rotor rotates in synchrony with the rotating magnetic field produced by the stator current. The speed of the motor is determined by the frequency of the supply voltage and the number of poles in the motor.

2.3 Magnetic Field Interaction: The interaction between the magnetic field of the stator and the permanent magnets on the rotor generates torque, allowing the motor to perform mechanical work.

2.4 Advantages

- **High Efficiency:** PMSMs typically have higher efficiency than induction motors, especially at lower speeds.
- **Compact Size and Weight:** The use of permanent magnets allows for a smaller and lighter design compared to other motor types.
- **High Torque Density:** PMSMs can produce high torque relative to their size, making them suitable for applications where space and weight are critical.

- **Low Maintenance:** Since there are no brushes or commutators, PMSMs require less maintenance compared to brushed motors.
- **Good Performance:** They offer excellent speed-torque characteristics and can operate efficiently across a wide range of speeds.

3. The motor:

The motor is a PMSM (permanent magnet synchronous motor) with a rotor position sensor, brief technical data are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Parameter name	Value
Rated shaft torque, M_n , Nm	21
Rated rotational speed, n_n , rpm	2000
Rated current, I_n , A	10
Maximum current, I_{max} , A	28

4. The load:

The asynchronous motor operates in generator mode and serves to create a moment on a synchronous motor in order to simulate the loads on the electric motor of the simulator drive created by the propeller under various modes of movement of the vessel.

As an asynchronous motor, the speed sensor is used; brief technical data of the asynchronous electric motor are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Parameter name	Value
Rated power P_h , kW	3
Rated shaft torque, M_n , Nm	20.4
Rated speed, n_n , rpm	1400
Rated current, I_n , A	6.5
$\cos\phi$	0.83
Efficiency at 75% load	84.5

at 100 % load	83
Inrush current to rated, current ratio current, I_n/I_H	$I_n 5,6$
Ratio of starting torque to nominal M_p/M_n	2,7

5. Simulator work characteristics :

The simulator work consists of two electric motors – asynchronous and synchronous on one shaft connected by a coupling and mounted on a metal frame. They can be controlled either from the local controls located on the front panel of the drive control cabinet, or from a personal computer designed for entering parameters when setting up motor and load characteristics, remote control of the drives, processing and displaying test results.

The simulator work is powered from a three-phase network of $380V \pm 10\%$, $50Hz \pm 5\%$.

5.1 Technical specifications

The standard characteristics of the simulator work for long-term operation of the drive are shown in Table 3.

Technical Specifications Table 3

Output voltage	0-380 V
0-380 V Rated	power 3 kW
Rated current	7A
Maximum power	4.5 kW
Maximum current	10A
Operating range of output frequency converters	0-100 Hz
Motor type	Asynchronous and synchronous
Input voltage 380 V Power	380 V
supply frequency	50Hz
Power supply side converter	6-pulse diode rectifier
Inverter type	3-level (PWM) with fixed neutral point
Cooling	Air transport
Control system Air supply voltage	24 V DC
PWM frequency	4-8kHz

Storage temperature	-20 to 60°C
Operating ambient temperature	0 to 40°C
Humidity	5 to 95% Non-condensing
Altitude	<1000m above sea level
Installation	Indoor installation
Color	RAL7035
Protection class	IP21
Engine control type	Vector control with position sensor
Control sources	Local control, remote control

5.2 Simulator work components:

The simulator work consists of:

- Input and adjustment of parameters of up to 8 motor (limiting the task for the frequency converter controlling the motor) and up to 8 load (forming the task for the frequency converter controlling the load) characteristics;
- Control of drives based on the selected characteristics in local (control via the drive control cabinet) and remote (from the remote control of a personal computer (PC)).
- Display of drive parameters on the doors of the drive control cabinet and on the PC screen, providing the operator with the opportunity to view, save, and print graphs of the status signals of frequency converters.

6. Conducting experimental studies:

A total of 8 motor characteristics are available, and we can select a custom characteristic by clicking on the 1-8 buttons at the bottom of the frame, motor characteristics and their parameter sets:

1) Motor characteristic #1-Constant speed operation – the motor rotates at a constant speed regardless of the load on the shaft, one value is set – the speed, no others parameters are set.

2) Motor characteristic #2-Constant power operation – the motor is limited in power, and the maximum torque (current) and speed are also limited, one value is set – the speed.

Parameters: maximum power, W (up to 3000W), maximum torque (current) modulus,%, maximum speed modulus (the limit is set in all 4 quadrants).

Fig. 1 setting up motor characteristics

6.1 Mode 1. The electric drive (motor) operates at a constant speed.

The motor rotates with $n = \text{constant}$ regardless of the load on the shaft.

The following characteristics are used:

Motor - No.1 Load - No.1

In the engine speed setting window, we set the speed $n = 1000$ rpm.

In the window setting the moment, values of torque M from 0% to 100% are entered sequentially; the IF-1, IF-2 and drive parameters are entered in Table 4.

n Motor (rpm)	Udc motor if-1 (V)	F motor IF-1 (Hz)	Ioutput motor if-1 (A)	U output motor if-1 (V)	M load (%)	Udc load IF-2 (V)	F load IF-2 (Hz)	Ioutput load IF-2 (A)	Uoutput load IF-2 (In)
1000	560	49.9	0.5	63.5	0	556	-33.3	3	20.3
	559	49.9	1.6	336.9	20	851	-33	2.7	-75.9
	559	50	2.8	380	40	851	-32.5	3.0	-184.3
	547	50	4.1	365.6	60	868	-32	3.7	-255

	552	50	5.7	377.7	80	853	-31.6	4.4	-297
	556	50	6.9	366.1	100	854	-31.2	5.0	-316

Table 4: Experimental values at n= 1000 (rpm) - const; M load (%) - var;

Fig .2. Experimental results the electric drive operating at a constant speed

Fig 3. Reverse test

6.2 Mode 2. Operation of the electric drive with constant power:

In the engine performance window, the engine (motor) is limited by speed and torque:

$$|n|_{max} = 1200 \text{ rpm}; |M|_{max} = 100\%; |M| = |P/n|; |P| = |M|n|.$$

The following characteristics are used:

Motor - No.2

Load - No.1

In the speed setting window, the initial speed is set to 1200 rpm.

In the window setting the moment, the values $M_{(torque)}$ from 0% to 100% are entered sequentially.

Enter the IF-1, IF-2 and drive parameters in Table 5.

Table 5: n max = 1200rpm; M heating– var; ln=1000rpm| -1; lM=100%| -1; lPl= /Mn|

n motor (rpm)	DC motor IF -1	F motor IF-1	Ioutput motor IF-1 (A)	Uoutput motor IF-1 (V)	M load (%)	Udc load IF-2 (V)	F load IF-2 (Hz)	Ioutput load IF-2	Uoutput Load IF-2
1200	560	59.9	0.6	357.7	0	567	-39.8	2.2	-44.8
1199	556	59.9	1.5	405	20	866	-39.5	2.4	-137
1169	560	58.5	2.9	433.6	40	869	-37	3.1	-276.5
756	556	37.9	4.2	285.6	60	858	-24.3	3.9	-163.3
566	556	28.4	5.7	208	80	852	-17.6	4.5	-146.3
1	557	0.3	7.1	37.7	100	559	1.7	5.2	2.3

Fig .4 Experimental results operation of the electric drive with constant power

Fig.5 Reverse test

6.3 Mode 3. Recording drive characteristics under different operating conditions of the propeller:

The load moment varies according to the parabolic law $M = a \cdot n^b + c$ depending on the speed of rotation of the screw

To simulate various operating conditions of the screw (clean water, intermediate mode, sludge operation), the coefficients $a = 0.00005$; $a = 0.0001$; $a = 0.0002$ are set sequentially (the coefficients "b" and "c" remain constant at $b = + 2.0$; $c = + 3$).

The following characteristics are used:

engine - No. 1. load - #2.

Parameters of IF-1, IF-2 with different coefficients "a" and changes in the engine speed should be entered in Tables 6, 7 and 8

Table 6 ($a = 0.00005$, $b = 2$, $c = 3$)

n motor (rpm)	Udc IF-1 (V)	F IF-1 (Hz)	Ioutput output if-1 (A)	Uoutput output if-1 (V)	Udc IF-2 (V)	F IF-2 (Hz)	Ioutput output IF-2 (A)	Uoutput output IF-2
200	561	9.9	0.8	57	562	-6.6	3	0
400	561	19.9	1.1	149.9	565	-13.1	3.1	-6.9

600	558	29.9	1.7	213.6	636	-19.8	3.2	-41.2
800	546	39.9	2.6	257	869	-26.1	3.5	-95.8

Fig .6. Experimental results operating of the propeller in clean (open) water

Fig.7 Variation of the load moment with the variation of the electric drive speed variation (characteristic 2, a = 0.00005)

Table 7 (a= 0.0001, b=2, c=3)

n motor (rpm)	Udc IF-1 (V)	F IF-1 (Hz)	Ioutput output if-1 (A)	Uoutput output if-1 (V)	Udc IF-2 (V)	F IF-2 (Hz)	output output IF-2 (A)	Uoutput output IF-2 (V)
200	558	9.9	1.0	66.1	558	-6.6	3	-1.8
400	562	19.9	1.5	140.4	564	-13.2	3.1	-20.7
600	558	29.9	2.8	218.9	860.9	-19.4	3.4	-85.4
800	561	39.9	4.9	295.8	867	-25.5	4.1	-185.3

Fig .8. Experimental results operating of the propeller in intermediate mode

Fig.9 Variation of the load moment with the variation of the electric drive speed variation (characteristic 2, a = 0.0001)

Table 8 (a= 0.0002, b=2, c=3)

n motor (rpm)	Udc IF-1 (V)	F IF-1 (HzHz)	Ioutput output if-1 (A)	Uoutput output if-1 (V)	Udc IF-2 (V)	F IF-2 (HzHz)	Ioutput output IF-2 (A)	Uoutput output IF-2 (V)
200	557	9.9	1.2	31.7	560	-6.5	3.1	-5.5
400	557	19.9	2.6	124.8	861	-12.8	3.4	-50
600	553	29.9	5.5	217.7	856	-18.8	4.3	-41.2
800	551	39.9	6.9	289.6	859	-25	5.0	-155.1

Fig .10. Experimental results operating of the propeller in sludge operation

Fig.11 Variation of the load moment with the variation of the electric drive speed variation (characteristic 2, a = 0.0002)

7. Results and Discussion

7.1 The motor rotates with $n = \text{constant}$ regardless of the load on the shaft:

The motor voltage on the DC is almost constant when the load changes, which indicates good power stabilization. The currents and voltages outputs increase with increasing load (torque) to create more motor power in order to support the load imposed and maintain motor performance.

The negative values of load frequency indicate the current direction. They are also almost constants; it means that the load speed is also constant, and there is a slight adjustment in frequency to account for the load demands. The system appears to be regulated by both inverters (IF-1 and IF-2), with voltage and current scaling as the load increases, ensuring the motor can support the different load levels effectively and with constant speed.

7.2 Mode 2. Operation of the electric drive with constant power:

By increasing the load, the motor speed decreases, the motor current increases and reaches the peak 7.1A at 100% of torque in order to maintain the power constant, that concludes the torque–current relationship, the motor frequency decreased by decreasing motor speed indicates direct proportionality between frequency and motor speed, which is expected behavior in variable-frequency drives

7.3 Mode 3. Recording drive characteristics under different operating conditions of the propeller:

The electric motor current increases significantly with motor speed: from 0.8A at low speed to 2.6A at high speed, showed increased electrical demand as the motor works more at higher speeds in order to create more power for the propeller and overcome the resistance posed by the environment conditions.

Negative voltages of the load correspond to energy recovery of braking modes, because in sludge mode the system applies reverse thrust to avoid getting stuck, resulting in energy being fed back into the system.

The motor frequency increased linearly with motor speed, ranging from 9.9Hz at 200 rpm to 39.9Hz at 800 rpm indicates direct proportionality between frequency and motor speed, which is expected behavior in variable-frequency drives.

Gradual increasing of load current from 3A to 3.5A indicates consistent performance despite varying conditions and balanced power distribution even under dynamic conditions.

Output Voltage IF-2 showed negative voltages (-0V to -95.8V) due to regenerative braking effects.

8. Conclusion:

The experimental study provides valuable insights into the performance characteristics of a synchronous motor driving another asynchronous motor as a load. The findings indicate that while the motors can operate effectively in this configuration, in different environment conditions.

Currently, the synchronous propulsion motor and frequency converter with a direct current link based on autonomous inverters and uncontrolled rectifiers The AC rowing electric installation utilizing a synchronous electric motor, solid-state frequency converter, and load device demonstrate a highly efficient and adaptable solution for the power plants on modern ships applications [7-8].

The simulator system demonstrated stable operation over the entire load ranges and successfully adapted to varying load conditions, making it suitable for challenging environments conditions. The electrical parameters change predictably, which confirms the correctness of the simulator control algorithms. It allows safely exploring the limits of operation and optimizing control settings to increase efficiency and reliability.

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